

Challenges Faced by Teachers Upon the Implementation of ‘2023- Zambia’s Competence-Based Curriculum’: A Case Study on Secondary Schools in Mansa District of Luapula Province

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ABSTRACT

Zambia has moved from outcome-based to Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) in 2023. The purpose of the CBC is to respond to individual, national, continental and global needs. Implementation phase started in 2025 and was characterized by a delayed supply of educational materials to kick-start the whole process. Ministry of Education through the directorate of curriculum development centre had the mandate to train master trainers, trainer of trainers and teachers to successfully implement it. Hence, the current research intends to bring out the challenges associated with the implementation of the new curriculum in order to develop mitigation strategies. To fill the research gap, the study being reported in this article was undertaken. This paper aims at the qualitative approach using descriptive survey. Analytical data was collected from Speeches, Zambia Competence-Based Curriculum Framework 2023 and reports about the challenges faced by implementers of the new curriculum. Data collection was made through focus group discussions, interviews and school visits using a sample size of 42 people which comprised of two District Education Standard Officers and forty Subject Teachers randomly selected in Mansa District. Results indicated challenges associated with the implementation of the new curriculum in its’ initial stage. These challenges included teachers not adequately prepared to implement Competence-Based Curriculum, late arrival of syllabi and modules; Lack of trained teachers for some new subjects introduced such as ICT (Information & Computer Technology); teachers facing the difficulty of adjusting abruptly to Competence-Based Methodologies; lack of training in School Based Assessment, and lack of full understanding of the Curriculum pathways and how to handle them. Suggestion have been made to overcome the challenges identified. Suggestions have also been made for timely provision of validated final copies of the syllabi and text books since these materials are key elements for the implementation of the new curriculum; adequate training of teachers for effective implementation of CBC; timely deployment of trained teachers in secondary schools for new subjects introduced in the education system; and speedy construction of Computer laboratories in some secondary schools before the election year of 2026.

Keywords: Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC), ICT (Information and Computer Technology) & OBE (Outcome Based Education)

INTRODUCTION

Zambia is a country located in Southern Africa. Its population is estimated to be 19, 610,769 in 2022 (Zambia Statistics Agency, 2022) and it is a former British Colony, whose economy is dominated by copper production. Educationally, Zambia inherited British Education system and as a matter of policy, its’ curriculum was reviewed periodically to determine its relevance in meeting individual, national, continental and global needs. In 2023, Zambia migrated from outcome-based to

Competence- Based Curriculum. Nonetheless the implementation of 2023 Competence-Based Curriculum commenced in 2025, and it faced many challenges. Therefore, the paper is intended to focus on the Challenges faced in the implementation of a Competence- Based Curriculum.

Problem Statement

The implementation of CBC in Zambia in its initial stage was problematic. The process was marked by challenges such as inadequacy and teacher

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competency to cater to the new curriculum, and untimely supply of teaching and learning materials for the timely implementation. It is the focus of this paper to highlight the challenges and the proposed strategies to the effective implementation of CBC.

Specific Objectives

- To examine challenges faced by the teachers upon the implementation of Competence- Based Curriculum in 2023.
- To evolve the strategies towards effective implementation of a Competence-Based Curriculum.

Research Questions

- What are challenges faced by the teachers during the implementation phase of a Competence-Based Curriculum?
- What are strategies to be evolved to enhance effective implementation of a Competence-Based Curriculum?

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are many diverse meanings for the term curriculum and has there defined by many. . According Doll (1978) curriculum can be viewed as the formal and informal contents and processes by which learners gain knowledge and understanding, develop skills, and alter attitudes, appreciations and values under the auspices of that school. A curriculum is said to be either content or competent based: 'a content-based curriculum is based on the rote memorization of factual knowledge while competence-based curriculum capitalizes on competence-based learning which focuses on understanding the concepts, skills and competencies which in turn calls for changes in teaching, learning and assessment approaches (Posner, 1995). In 2023, Zambia moved from outcome-based curriculum to Competence-Based Curriculum.

History of Competence-Based Curriculum

The launch of a competence-based curriculum can be traced back to the early 1970s in the United States of America (Richard & Rogers, 2001) and eventually spread into European countries such as the United

Kingdom and Germany in the 1980s (Wolf, 2001). Australia adopted the competence-based curricula in the 1990s. Other countries worldwide have been motivated to implement the competence-based curriculum in schools due to the ever changing technology and global market (Komba et al., 2012). Furthermore, the CBC was also adopted by other countries including New Zealand, and a many European countries (Finch and Crunkiton, 1999). In Africa, competence-based curriculum was adopted for the first time in South Africa in 1998 (Komba and Mwandangi, 2015), Other African, countries such as Rwanda, Zambia, Tanzania, Nigeria, Kenya and Ethiopia have also adopted the CBC (Nsengimana et al, 2020). In most of developing countries, the CBC was adopted from developed countries and adapted to the specific needs of the country (Muraraneza, Mtshali and Mukamana, 2017).

Challenges faced in the Implementation of Competence- Based Curriculum in other Countries.

Rwanda

Nsengimana (2021) reported challenges accompanying the Implementation of Competence-Based Curriculum in Rwanda. His research findings revealed that major challenges included the lack of teaching and learning materials, laboratory equipment and chemical reagents. Teachers suggested collaboration between the government and other education stakeholders to overcome the identified challenges.

Indonesia

Utomo (2005) conducted a study on challenges of curriculum reform in the context of decentralization in Indonesia. The study sought to reveal teachers' responses following the implementation of competence-based curriculum in schools. The findings showed that the in- service primary school teachers were equipped with only one third of the training needed for effective implementation of competence-based curriculum. As such, they were unable to implement it in the classroom and continued to use the traditional ways of teaching which are based on content.

South Africa

In addition, Mlaudzi (2009) conducted a study in South Africa whose main objective was to investigate how educators in South Africa perceived the Outcome Based Education (OBE) system. It was argued that students were required to demonstrate the skills and course contents they have learnt. The findings revealed that the successful implementation of OBE was hampered by lack of resources and lack of professional framework of continuing professional development and support programmes.

Tanzania

Kafyulilo et al., (2012) conducted a study on the implementation of competence-based teaching approaches in Tanzania. In this study, the authors revealed that pre-service teachers needed a kind of practices with the competence-based teaching approaches in order to be able to effectively implement the approaches in their teaching. Komba and Mwandani (2015) found the need to conduct a study to investigate the implementation of competence-based curriculum in the context of Tanzanian secondary schools. The study sought to achieve specific objectives such as: to examine the teachers' understanding of the objectives of competence-based curriculum; to investigate the teachers' abilities in preparing competence-based lesson plans; to examine whether or not teachers involve students in classroom activities; and to find out whether or not teachers practice formative students' assessments. The study reviewed that the majority of the interviewed teachers did not have the proper understanding of the objectives of competence-based curriculum. In addition, the majority of the reviewed lesson plans did not reflect the qualities of a competence-based lesson plan. Moreover, the involvement of students in classroom activities by the teachers who were observed was, in overall, very low. Lastly, teachers practiced formative students' assessments in less than 50% of the observed classroom sessions. In view of the findings, it seemed that the implementation of competence-based curriculum in the selected schools was ineffective. The study recommended that regular training for in-service teachers should be conducted in order to enable them acquire up-to-date teaching skills as required by the changes introduced in the school

curricula. Zambia in 2023 too moved from Outcome-Based Curriculum to Competence-Based Curriculum. Like other studies conducted in other countries, Challenges accompanying the implementation of CBC is recorded and investigated the outcome.

Theoretical Frame work

This study aims at identifying challenges and makes suggestion to mitigate such challenges in relation to the CBC implementation in Zambia. This study adopts the curriculum implementation theory developed by Gross, Giacuinta and Bernstein (1971). This theory indicates that for successful implementation of any educational program, factors such as teacher awareness and attitudes must be taken into consideration. Further, the theory indicates that when [the] teacher is not aware of changes in curriculum, the implementation may not be effective and adequate. Further, the teacher may have positive attitudes towards the curriculum and changes contained in the curriculum, and thereby contribute to its implementation (as cited in Nsengimana, 2021).

Policy Framework for Curriculum Formulation and Implementation Phases

The Competence-Based Curriculum was formulated in response to Global, Continental, National and Individual needs. It took into consideration integrating cross-cutting issues highlighted in the Curriculum Frame work.

Global Level: Sustainable Development Goals

2023 Zambia Competence-Based curriculum resonates well with sustainable development Goal number 4 which mandates member states to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education [provision] and promote life-long learning opportunities for all (2023, Zambia Education curriculum Frame work, p.3).

Continental Level: Agenda 2063

The new curriculum was aligned with the African Union Agenda 2063 and the Continental Education Strategy for Africa (2023, Zambia Education curriculum Frame work, p.3).

2.1.3 Country Level Vision 2030

The 2023 competence-based curriculum was developed and aligned with the nation long term plan, the vision 2030 and its main aim is to attain middle income status by 2030 in Zambia (2023, Zambia Education curriculum Frame work p, 6). Additionally, the new curriculum took into consideration what was set in the **eighth National development plan**. The 8NDP sets to enhance access to quality, equitable and inclusive education; to improve Technical Education, Vocational and Entrepreneurship Training; increase access to higher education and enhance science, technology and innovation. The plan further guided that curriculum will be reviewed to ensure that it provides life-relevant knowledge and skills and promote the application of national values and principles. Legally the main piece of legislation that informed its formulation was the Education Act 2011 though other national and international instruments were consulted (2023 Zambia Education Curriculum Frame work pp6-7).

Education for Sustainability, 2023: The new curriculum was developed to respond to the aspirations of the proposed new education policy, education for sustainability (2023 Zambia Education Curriculum Frame work p6). Other policies too were considered in its formulation.

Zambia's Education Curriculum Frame Work for a Competence-Based Curriculum 2023. The Curriculum frame work highlighted cross-cutting issues integrated into the curriculum such as Life skills and Health education, Gender, Governance, Corruption, Human Rights and Freedoms, National Values and Principles, Entrepreneurship Education, HIV/AIDs, Environmental Health and Pollution Management, Climate Change Education, Health and Nutrition, Drug and substance abuse, Mental Health, Social and Emotional Learning, Financial Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Education for Sustainable Development and Digital literacy . The guiding principles that informed curriculum formulation were inclusiveness and equity, accountability, transparency, partnerships, social justice and integrity. The 2023 Zambian curriculum is a Competence-Based curriculum, and English language is the official language of instruction from early Childhood Education to tertiary level. (2023 Zambia Education Curriculum Frame work p, 9).

Curriculum reforms highlighted briefly

In the preface of the 2023 Zambia Education Curriculum Frame work, Mr. Joel Kamoko, then Permanent Secretary-Education Services highlighted curriculum reforms. The 2023 curriculum had adjusted the structure of the education system from 4-7-2-3 to 3-6-4-2. The ECE had been reduced from 4 to 3 years while primary had been reduced from 7 to 6 years. The secondary education level had been restructured and increased from 5 to 6 years to accommodate 2 years of A-levels. Learner would have 4 years of ordinary level and 2 years of advanced secondary education. Forms have replaced Grades at secondary school level. The new curriculum showed clear linkages at all levels of education from ECE to tertiary education and youth and adult literacy education. In addition, the new curriculum had provided eight career pathways for learners to have an opportunity to progress according to their abilities and interests. The new curriculum had integrated cross-cutting issues and emerging issues... in order to respond to societal needs. The curriculum frame work had also emphasised on the use of Information and Communications Technology in teaching and learning, management and research through the provision of innovative, technology-based education programmes and services as well as the promotion of STEM education. Automatic progression from primary to secondary school has been abolished together with the Junior Secondary School leaving Examination. Learners have to pass the examination at Grade 6 to proceed to Form 1. In addition, Candidates would write their School Certificate examination at the end of Form 4. It was expected that the Competence- Based Curriculum would equip learners at all levels of education with vital competences, knowledge, skills and values that are necessary for the actualization of [a long-term nation plan], the vision 2030 (a quote extracted and rearranged by the author, 2023 Zambia Education Curriculum Frame work, p.x).

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

This paper used qualitative approach using descriptive survey. Analytical data was collected from Speeches, Zambia Competence-Based Curriculum Framework 2023, reports about the challenges faced by implementers of the new curriculum. In addition,

Field data was collected from Education Officers (2) in Mansa district and Teachers (40) from randomly selected secondary schools by using semi-interview and researchers' observation to confirm what was discussed about the implementation of the 2023 curriculum.

Findings On Challenges During The Implementation Phase Of 2023 Competence-Based Curriculum

Research question number 1: what challenges teachers faced during the implementation phase of a Competence- Based Curriculum?

The curriculum frame work had provided strategies for effective implementation. It was expected to follow four phases namely preparation, pilot or pretest, roll out and 2023 curriculum review. It spelt out how resources could be mobilized and managed. Further, it stated that "successful implementation of the curriculum requires adequate supply of educational support materials and infrastructure such as practical subject equipment, textbooks, teaching aids, science and computer laboratories and specialized rooms necessary for the provision of quality education to the learners. There is need for Government to develop and procure all necessary Curriculum support materials for the successful implementation of the curriculum."(2023 Zambia Education Curriculum Frame work p, 44) Despite such nice pronouncements, teachers had challenges in implementing the new curriculum. These were as follow:

Teachers were not adequately prepared to implement Competence-Based Curriculum:

Though trainings were conducted for Master trainers and Trainers of Trainers, they did not fully acquaint themselves on how to handle a Competence-Based Curriculum. One teacher remarked "As a teacher I am not ready to start teaching a competence-based curriculum since I have no idea of what it is and what should be done. As teachers, we were supposed to be capacity-built in the effective implementation of CBC before opening of schools in term 1, 2025. Sensitization and Workshops about CBC were done after opening of schools in term1 of 2025 contrary to my expectation."

Late arrival and supply of syllabi and modules. A question was posed as to when syllabi and textbooks would be distributed to all schools. This question was pertinent to start implementation of CBC. Contrary to what Curriculum Framework had proposed about distribution of Materials, syllabi and Modules were not in schools in Mansa district of Luapula Province at a time when the Form 1s were reporting. It was extremely difficult for teachers to begin teaching Form 1s without such teaching resources. One teacher remarked "I could not prepare Schemes of Work and Lesson Plans for my Class in my Subject because schools had not received syllabi and Modules." Contrary to a well-known practice of distributing "Hard Copies syllabi", Teachers could down load "Soft Copies syllabi" since hard copies were not available at a time when Form 1s were reporting. Those teachers in far-flung areas where internet connectivity was a challenge could not even down load soft copy syllabi. In some secondary schools, teachers were instructed by their Head teachers not to begin teaching awaiting the arrival of hard copies of Syllabi.

Teachers facing the difficult of adjusting abruptly to Competence-Based Methodologies: Some teaching methods spelt out in the 2023 CBC Framework were quite new and needed more resources. A Competence-Based Curriculum had put emphasis on a learner demonstrating what they have learnt as opposed to acquiring "head knowledge". It had assumed that learners doing what they have learnt, is a sign that they have fully understood what they are doing.

Lack of trained teachers for some new subjects introduced. For example, CBC had introduced Computer Science which demanded trained teachers. Previously teachers were trained to teach Computer studies, they had to negotiate and gravitate cautiously to enable them teach Computer Science which they were not trained for. Perhaps, the policy makers had assumed that teachers trained to teach Computer Studies would as well teach Computer Science and ICT. One teacher said "if I had a challenge of teaching Computer studies since computers were not provided at my school, how will I teach Computer Science?"

Lack of training in School Based Assessment: In the initial stage of the implementation of CBC, one

teacher said i have not received training on how to conduct a CBC School-Based Assessment which the framework proposed would be added to the final grade in summative examinations at Form 4 in Mathematics II.

Lack of full understanding of the Curriculum pathways and how to handle them: The 2023 Competence-Based Curriculum Framework had proposed Ordinary School pathways which teachers did not fully understand. In the previous curriculum (that is 2013 Outcome-Based Curriculum), the pathways were divided neatly into Academic and Vocational pathways. Though the Zambia Education Curriculum Framework stated that “placing of learners in different pathways shall be done based on the results obtained at the end of the primary education examination and the interest of learners”, the process was not rigidly followed. The practice was that most secondary schools chose pathways depending on the availability of teaching staff. In fact, Teachers could argue out to what and how many pathways to put in each class (The researcher witnessed such a happening at one school during his field visit). Though there was a workshop to guide what should be done, “confusion” had erupted to whether or not Non-STEM Schools (not explicitly stated in the framework) could adopt STEM pathways (not until an addendum was sent to what should have been done). One teacher at Non-STEM school said “I don’t still understand to whether my Form 1pupils ought to be taking Mathematics II offered in STEM schools since my class is given Design and Technology Curriculum.”

Research question 2: what strategies can be provided to effectively implement a Competence-Based Curriculum?

During my field research, teachers provided a number of solutions to the Challenges they were facing. These were as follows:

Adequate training of teachers for effective implementation of CBC: One Teacher said “Future curriculum implementation should consider adequate training of implementers well in advance a year before rolling out the curriculum. This would enable implementers reflect on so many issues such as tenability of syllabus, teaching quotient, so and so

forth.” Teachers also therefore highlighted the need to involve many teachers as opposed to few members on the panel in the process of drafting and validating the syllabi.

Timely provision of validated or final copies of the syllabi and text books since these materials are key in the implementation of the new curriculum. One teacher of Religious Education at a certain secondary school said “I am unable to prepare my scheme of work since the school has not received the syllabus”

Timely deployment of trained teachers in secondary schools for new subjects introduced in the education system: One teacher at a certain secondary said I am alone in my section as a computer studies teacher who would be required to teach ICT. i think government could have deployed more teachers of ICT and capacity-build service-teachers through workshops and conferences to enable them deal with new and emerging issues during the implementation phase.

Speed construction of Computer laboratories before the election year of 2026. Teachers expressed fear that if Construction of such facilities is delayed, it would hamper effective implementation of the Competence-Based curriculum. In addition, they suggested speed provisions of Computers to enable secondary schools effectively teach ICT and Computer Science to march the digital needs of our learners in the 21st Century.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The 2023 competence-based curriculum brought changes into the education system which needed adequate teacher preparation and readiness to implement it. The whole education structure drastically changed to a 3-6-4-2, totally different from 2013 Education structure. The 3-6-4-2 structure implied 3 years of Early childhood education, 6 years of Primary education, 4 years of ordinary secondary education, 2 years of A-level Secondary Education and 3 years of Tertiary Education. By implication, the whole educational system had to be adjusted to suit the changes. Education Act of 2011 were supposed to be revised to suit the new education structure. For example 2023 competence-Based Framework abolished junior secondary which was supposed to be

reflected in the Education Act. It is not always clear what ought to come first, policy or legal instrument operationalizing the education system. The second challenge was late distribution of syllabi and Textbooks essential for its effective implementation. Master trainers and Trainer of Trainers failed to answer well the question to when such resource materials would be distributed or made available in schools. In fact at the time of implementing the new curriculum, they were no textbooks (author was a teacher and had made this observation). It was stated that Modules would be developed and be used as teaching tools. Syllabi down loaded and printed proved to be too costly, and Subject Teachers in secondary schools had to bear the cost. In some remote areas, where internet connectivity was and still a challenge, teachers could not access soft copy syllabi. It is the mandate of CDC to ensure it distributes approved hard copy syllabi to all schools. This too requires timely planning, preparation and financial resources do so. The third challenge was lack of full understanding of the curriculum pathways and how to implement them. This brought confusion to whether or not STEM pathway can be offered in Non-STEM schools. Poor or lack of understanding poses a challenge to how the whole curriculum would be handled. Though the framework had given to offer learners choice on career pathways, learners themselves were not adequately oriented about the new curriculum (in some schools Form 1s were not given an opportunity to choose) not because teachers did not want but it was because they lacked understanding about the whole process. It is imperative that teachers should be involved in Curriculum Preparation and Formulation to enable them understand fully what ought to be done. Fourth, before introducing new subject, MOE should track the availability of trained teachers to teach those new subjects rather than riding on an assumption that for example a teacher trained to teach computer studies would teach Computer Science. This may be against professional ethos of a trained teacher teaching the subject he/ she was not trained for. If available fewer teachers in the related field or subject are incapable of handling newer subjects (a case of computer studies teachers to teach ICT and Computer Science), it would be appropriate to capacity-build them or reskill them through Continuing Professional Development programs. Firth, Competence-Based Curriculum

highlighted the need to build Science and Computer Laboratories. These were capital projects and ought to have taken off before the roll out of the curriculum. When the researchers toured selected secondary schools, almost all science laboratories were “white elephants” turned into classrooms. Even in the few well-equipped laboratories, experimentation and discovery as teaching methods were rarely used. For Computer Science laboratories sampled, few and old computers were found, some not even functional or broken down, and rarely accessed or utilized by learners due to power outages. Though some schools had “gensets” as alternative source of power, they proved to be costly running them due to high fuel prices.

CONCLUSION

The Implementation phase of CBC in Zambia was hurriedly done revealing a number of loopholes such as inadequate Teacher preparation for CBC to kick start. There were no available hard copy syllabi and modules in schools at the time of starting its implementation; Teachers were inadequately prepared and lacked readiness; Science and Computer laboratories were not well equipped in most secondary schools in Mansa district to enable teachers utilize experimentation and discovery methods recommended by CBC.

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